

Distinctive Features of Pedagogical Technology for the Formation of Communicative Skills of Mentally Retarded Students of the Primary Class

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Abstract:

This article examines the types of activities for developing communication skills of mentally retarded primary school students, in which attention should be paid to the features of pedagogical technology.

Keywords: mental retardation, epilepsy, schizophrenia, empathy, sympathy, ability to hear, argumentation autistic, sensory perception, internal emotional control, tolerance, maintaining one's own point of view (worldview), expressing one's feelings and desires, clarity, openness, self-awareness, low aggression.

The development of communicative skills of mentally retarded students can be carried out slowly. Mentally retarded students rarely experience mental retardation after the formation of their speech. One manifestation of this condition is called dementia (insanity). Deficiency in intellectual salinity, changes in the mental state of the outbreak of the disease are observed when dementia is not given importance. Especially there is a mental illness (epilepsy, schizophrenia), defects in mentally retarded students are evident, and the development of such children leads to negative States. The lack of activity in mentally retarded students, symptoms of inability to control one's own actions, make new reflexes more troublesome due to lack in the cranial brain. In mentally retarded students, their interest in knowledge and extirpation are below the norm, therefore, depending on their age, simple physiological needs are observed, for example, the need for food

Correctional training is essential for mentally retarded Archers who cannot independently master,

concentrate, assimilate the information around them. Under specially organized conditions, Ham, the rate of development of mentally retarded students changes very slowly and significantly. While a healthy reader has mastered the data under his own power, a mentally retarded reader will absorb it with extreme weariness, continuously returning as his or her mastery is low. Since the level of knowledge is not enough, long work is required for them to know and learn, of course, it must be strengthened. Various obstacles interfere with the organization of interaction between children and parents. Including the “barrier” of being busy, parents are constantly busy, unable to pay attention to the child, because they have a lot of household chores. This leads to a cessation of emotional development in the child.

The second obstacle is an age-related "obstacle", in which adults do not understand the child because they are older. They cannot take into account the inner world of the child. What is not worth for an adult can be important for a child. Old mold "dust" -parents do not notice that their child is getting older. As the child grows up, he wants his parents to reckon with him. Therefore, misunderstandings, conflicts arise between them. We want our adult children to listen to us all the time, we want them to obey us. We will melt to hear their independent thoughts. This means that adults should lose their old outlook on the child. Then the barrier in the middle disappears. The “barrier” in the educational tradition-parents use the methods of the previous educational influence in the family, do not take into account the degree of mental development of the child. They do not work on improving their qualifications. As a result, a barrier arises between the child and him, unable to understand each other.

Didacticism”barrier" -in this, parents constantly teach the child intelligence. Each step of the child is measured, evaluated. This creates tension in the child, becomes nervous. So, in order to lose the above “obstacles”, the parent needs to look for ways to communicate correctly with his child. Only then will they be able to find a language with the child.

To develop Correctional development work, first, knowledge of ways of correcting the communicative skills of mentally retarded students, as well as pedagogical technologies in correctional development are developed.

№	Communicative skills	Personal qualities of the reader	Pedagogical technologies in the development of Correction
1	Empathy	Feeling experiences knowing how to look at the world through the eyes of others	Boshqaruchi o'yinlar, pozitiv harakatli mashqlar
2	Kindness	To respect and like, understand and support others	Management games, positive movement exercises, body work
3	Knowing how to listen	Listening with patience, attention, benevolence, self-discipline	Free movement exercises, concentration, hearing and speech development exercises
4	Argue	patience, staying in one's judgments	exercises and games for free movement, speech development
5	Autistic	Self-awareness, self-confidence, self-assessment, self-respect,	Management games, leadership, self-awareness, exercises for support
6	Feeling the emotion	Expressing feelings and	Developing speech,

		accepting the feelings of others	enriching vocabulary, working with emotions
7	Controlling internal emotions	To be free	Working with anger, working on scandalous situations
8	Tolerance	Accepting others, taking into account their interests, opinions, and worldviews	Management games, active group games, positive movement exercises
9	Staying in one's own perspective (worldview)	Self-confidence, self-respect, knowing how to speak and act	Management games are exercises that develop leadership and speech
10	Expressing one's thoughts, feelings and wishes	Being able to talk about what they are thinking about, their emotional experiences	Exercises that develop interaction
11	Clarity	Talking about their experiences, answering questions accurately	Confidence-building, speech-building, exercises
12	Openness	Being ready to be open in the guru, persuasion,	Exercises that promote interaction
13	Self-awareness	Being ready to accept the opposite attitude from others, adequate self-evaluation	Management games and exercises, reflection, speech development exercises
14	Low aggression	To express one's opinion by arguing without quarrels. Self-control.	Management games, exercises on frustration, anger management, emotional management

When the development of personal characteristics in corrective development methods is analyzed and summarized, the communication of students with mental retardation is shown in Table 2. Correctional development of students with mental retardation includes: management games, self-control, concentration, speech development, vocabulary development, return and strengthening of communication methods, self-awareness and self-assessment, bold communication, striving to be the first (leadership).;

- Students' confidence in their classmates increases by forming action games;
- Body exercises, elements of relaxation;
- Exercises for anger and rage
- Exercises to behave in conflict situations;
- Verbal exercises for emotions and feelings, exercises for developing speech.

In the process of correctional development, it is necessary for mentally retarded students to familiarize themselves with exercises and management games, communication rules, and restore and strengthen communication methods based on pedagogical technologies.

Pedagogical technologies in the development of communicative skills in mentally retarded students have the following features: slowness of movement, inability to understand well, inability to understand, inability to remember and use information; not being able to absorb news, quickly forgetting the acquired knowledge, returning to and repeating the learned topic many times; lack of source of acquired knowledge; To consolidate the acquired knowledge and skills, it is necessary to work hard, otherwise they will forget them again.

In order to correct the development of students with mental retardation, it is necessary to return to the subject, reinforce it and repeat it many times.

In working with students with mental retardation - (Self-awareness and self-rewarding, making visible aspects invisible, in emotional situations) exercises in the form of games are more effective.

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